

ORGANIC ANALYTICAL REAGENTS CONTAINING SULPHUR.

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Dimercaptothiobiazole (Losanitsch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2544) and phenyldithiobiazolonthiol (Busch, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2511) having the reacting groups RN-CS-S-C (SH)=N , have been found to give coloured precipitates with the metals of the sulphide group.

The reagent dimercaptothiobiazole gives red precipitate with bismuth, white to yellow precipitate with other metals of the sulphide group, excepting mercury with which it gives a black precipitate, while the reagent phenyldithiobiazolonthiol gives yellow precipitates with gold, mercury, lead, silver, platinum, arsenic and antimony, white with cadmium and zinc, brown with copper, brick-red with tin and red precipitates with bismuth and palladium.

Dubsky and co-workers (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1934, 96, 267, 412) have used both the reagents for the detection of very small quantities of bismuth, their identification limit being 1.2 μg . and sensitivity 1 part in 28,000 parts.

Ray and Gupta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 308) found with the reagent dimercaptothiobiazole that the identification limit reaches 0.1 μg . and sensitivity one part in 1,600,000 parts if nitric and not hydrochloric acid solution of bismuth is used.

Recently it has been observed by the author that the red precipitates of the bismuth compounds given by both the reagents can be peptised by a solution of gum acacia of suitable concentration and that the colours developed can be used for the estimations of bismuth, as the intensity of colours varies regularly according to Beer's law.

Also it has been observed that the colouration limit with both the reagents reaches one part in 6,000,000 parts if a very dilute nitric acid solution of bismuth is used and that bismuth up to the extent of 37 in 20 c.c. solution can be estimated with a high degree of accuracy.

The details of the methods for the colorimetric estimations of bismuth as well as other possible uses of the reagents will be published shortly.